

INSIGHTS INTO ENGLISH MAJORS' UNHEARD-OF LEARNING ENCOUNTERS: THROUGH HUSSERLIAN PHENOMENOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This study stemmed from the need to capacitate English majors, especially those who had difficulties mastering the English language. Using Husserl's phenomenological approach, the researchers conducted in-depth interviews with English majors enrolled during the school year 2020-2021. For data analysis, Colaizzi's method was used, wherein the interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim, and then significant statements (SS) were extracted from the transcripts. The SS were then further analyzed to create formulated meanings (FMs), which were later organized to generate clusters of themes capturing the participants' overall experiences. The results reveal the emergent theme "Diverse Encounters While Learning" and the following subthemes: 1) Remarkable Scaffolds of Instructors; 2) Varied School Learning Activities; and 3) Numerous Learning Aids Utilized. It was found that teacher support plays an important role in motivating students to acquire English language proficiency. Furthermore, the participants claimed that engaging in school activities requiring them to use English and watching English TV programs and online videos help enhance their English language learning. Thus, the researchers concluded that exposure to the English language through school activities, digital media, and online sites, alongside appropriate scaffolding techniques from teachers, leads to students' competence in English. Therefore, the researchers suggested that English majors be further capacitated through proper scaffolding by instructors, taking into account the students' unique needs and backgrounds, and encouraging them to watch English TV shows and speak English at all times, especially on the campus premises.

Keywords: *colaizzi, English language learning, English majors, husserlian phenomenology, learning encounters, lived experiences, scaffolding,*

INTRODUCTION

A strong proficiency in English serves as a foundation for enhanced educational and employment prospects, as well as elevated social status (Al-Zoubi, 2018). Alharbi (2022) also discovered that a number of students were concerned about their chosen career path, which was why they would need a great amount of English language abilities. Nonetheless, learning a second language (L2)—including English—is highly intricate. Millions of individuals engage in L2 learning and often possess a practical understanding of the activities that facilitated their language acquisition (Mitchell et al., 2019). Indeed, numerous learning resources and activities have been found to help students learn English. For instance, Hamad et al. (2019), in their study on the impact of computer-assisted learning tools, found that employing YATI (YouTube videos and Audio Tracks Imitation) technique has a positive impact on the effectiveness of the speaking skills, fluency, and pronunciation of EFL learners majoring in English. Moreover, Suelto (2018) postulated that watching movies in English and listening to English-spoken media effectively improve English communication skills as students nowadays tend to adopt the way native speakers deliver the language. Despite this, mastering L2 like English presents significant challenges, and English majors are not exempt from these difficulties (Bacang et al., 2024), even after four years of studying English in college (Jackson et al., 2018).

Filipino researchers Futral et al. (2023), who conducted a two-case study in the Philippine setting, revealed the positive effects of digital learning materials, such as TV, on young children's English language acquisition. Her findings also proved that the lack of social interaction negatively impacts language acquisition. Recent research also reveals a decline in English proficiency among Filipinos, as confirmed by Suelto (2018), stating that the Philippines has lost its leading position in English proficiency in Asia. This claim is also backed by the EF English Proficiency Index (EPI) results for 2022, indicating the Philippines as only 22nd in rank out of 111 countries (EPI, 2022).

While aware that various learning materials and activities greatly help in facilitating English language learning, the researchers saw it alarming after observing that many of the English majors (who are supposedly future English teachers) lack spoken and written English abilities. Their concern for these students led the researchers to conduct an in-depth exploration of the English majors' encounters while learning the English language and other nuanced factors contributing to their learning. With this objective in mind, phenomenological research was pursued. This inquiry is unique since not much qualitative studies were done focusing on the English majors' lived experiences. Afzal (2019) focused only on the BA English majors' problems in terms of vocabulary learning, while Fontanilla (2016) examined the shifts in motivation and self-identity among English majors in the Philippines. Also, Zhang and Wang (2023) looked into how English learning motivation affects English majors' academic performance.

The current study, therefore, provides a more comprehensive investigation of the English majors and their world, shedding light on their journey as learners. The researchers hoped that, by delving into the students' lived experiences, they could come up with more effective English teaching strategies and interventions to aid students who chose to major in English to succeed not only in their academics but also in their future careers.

Research Question

This qualitative inquiry, which utilized the descriptive phenomenological approach, sought to answer the universal question:

What are the English majors' lived experiences in learning the English language?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically utilizing descriptive transcendental phenomenology, rooted in the philosophical framework of Edmund Husserl. Phenomenology aims to explore and understand the essence of individuals' everyday experiences. It focuses on describing phenomena as they are perceived by individuals, emphasizing the subjective nature of experience. This approach seeks to uncover the fundamental structures of consciousness and how these structures shape our understanding of the world. For this research, Colaizzi's method was adopted to systematically analyze and interpret the participants' lived experiences. Colaizzi's method, within this framework, provides a structured process for extracting, organizing, and elucidating the core themes from participants' narratives. This method ensures a rigorous and in-depth analysis, capturing the essence of the experiences being studied.

Research Locale

The interviews were conducted virtually via Zoom. Hence, the participants were in the safety and comfort of their homes when the study was conducted. This approach was necessary due to the pandemic, which at that time made in-person interviews risky for both the researchers and participants, especially given the increasing number of cases in the province.

Research Participants

This study involved six BSEd English students from Foundation University, each with at least two years of attendance. The participants were selected using purposive sampling based on specific inclusion criteria and the phenomenon under study. This non-probability sampling method relies on the researchers' knowledge to choose participants who are knowledgeable about the phenomenon. Despite its subjective nature, purposive sampling is common in qualitative research. According to Polit-O'Hara and Beck (2020),

all participants must have experienced the phenomenon and be able to articulate their experiences. The interviews continued until data saturation was reached, confirmed by interviewing a seventh participant.

Research Instrument

A semi-structured interview approach was utilized as the primary method for gathering data. The interview guide included open-ended questions in English. The questions were designed to elicit important insights from the participants and to provide clarity on the subject being investigated. The interviews were recorded automatically using Zoom. Additionally, the researchers kept a journal to document detailed notes and observations during the interviews.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection took place between March and April 2021. The researchers first obtained permission from the Dean of the College of Education to involve the English majors in the study. After approval, the researchers identified potential participants and contacted them via Messenger to arrange interviews based on their availability. The participants were thoroughly briefed about the study's purpose and confidentiality assurances. They signed informed consent forms and were informed about the recording of interviews via Zoom, with the option to withdraw at any time. During the interviews, the researchers listened attentively, only interrupting for clarifications, and guided the participants toward emerging themes. Notes on verbal and non-verbal cues, along with demographic information, were recorded in a journal. The interviews typically lasted between 30 minutes and 1 hour. The recorded interviews were transcribed and cross-referenced to ensure data accuracy, maintaining the integrity and reliability of the collected information.

RESULTS

After the researchers' thorough analysis of the transcripts and coding, one emergent theme was identified: Diverse Encounters while Learning. This major theme covers three subthemes, namely, 1) Remarkable Scaffolds of Instructors, 2) Varied School Learning Activities, and 3) Numerous Learning Aids Utilized.

"Diverse Encounters while Learning" explores the experiences of the participants as English majors. As students in the College of Education, one of the largest departments at Foundation University, they have maintained their confidence due to the support of their teachers, who consistently believe in their abilities. This encouragement has led them to actively participate in various university activities, including school campaigns, debates, and other curricular events.

To enhance their understanding of the English language, the participants frequently engage with books, YouTube videos, English movies, TV programs, and conversations with fluent speakers. Some even practice speaking English daily with friends and

classmates, despite occasional negative reactions from locals.

One participant, who has a long-term relationship with a British man, benefits from regular conversations with her boyfriend, which helps her improve her English speaking, listening, and comprehension skills.

Theme 1: Remarkable Scaffolds of Instructors

This theme talks about the English majors' experiences in terms of how their teachers push them to be better in their field.

Participant 5 has so much respect and appreciation for those teachers who supported her by teaching her what was wrong with her grammar or pronunciation in a constructive way. She recalled:

“...kanang pinaka-ganahan gyud nako kay katong mga teachers nga niagi sa akua nga kanang gina-correct bitaw ko ila every time lahi diay ang pronunciation. Kanang ma-appreciate kaayo nako sila, kung giunsa nila kanang ganahan sila nga mo improve jud ko. Mao na’y one of the reasons jud nga ganahan ko mopadayun sa pag acquire ani nga language kay kabalo ko naa ray mga tawo nga mo guide sa akua jud, just like sa mga mentors nga willing mo correct sa imoha if wrong grammar ka, if wrong imong pronunciation.”

“Just like naa ko’y teacher sa CE before nga wala siya ni correct pero ato nga time, diha pa ko kabalo nga ingon ana diay ang pronunciation sa “were” nga past tense sa “are” ba. Akoang pag pronounce ana sauna kay “where” raman gyud, where ba nga “asa.” So didto na learn nga lahi diay ang pronunciation. Unya dugay na kaayo from high school pa, ato pa ko naka learn nga college na...Those are the reasons nga nipadayun ko ag acquire ani nga language, tungod pod sa tabang sa mga tawo nga makapa boost sa akoang interest.”

Trans: (“What I really like was those teachers of mine who would really correct me whenever there was something off with my pronunciation. I really appreciate the fact that they also wanted me to improve. These were the reasons that I wanted to persist in acquiring the English language because I knew some people would guide me, just like those mentors who were willing to correct your errors in grammar or pronunciation.”

“Just like my teacher in CE before. Although she did not correct me at that time, I learned back then the proper pronunciation for ‘were,’ the past tense of ‘are.’ I used to pronounce it as ‘where,’ like the location. So I learned from her that my pronunciation was not right. To think it took me until college to learn the correct pronunciation... Those are the reasons that I continued to learn this language because of the help of those people, which also boosted

my interest.”)

Participant 4 also attested to how their English teachers showed them the relevance of the English language. She stated:

“Up to college, up till now, English teachers usually encourage us to speak in English because we are English majors...”

Theme 2: Varied School Learning Activities

Most of the participants in the current study have engaged in different forms of school activities. They see these activities as an avenue to express themselves and to also enhance their abilities in speaking, listening, and writing.

Participant 1, for instance, has been joining numerous school activities all throughout her student life. She said:

“My experiences in English, as an English major, during my first year, I was able to join the Foundation University school campaign and it also helped me develop my English speaking skill especially when dealing with different students from different schools.”

She went on to say:

“More engagements were given to me. Like, research or debates. First time nako nga gi send, because...sa junior high school, wala pa ko ka try og research sa N.O. so wala pa’y mga defense. So sa grade 11, naka try ko nga naa’y debate on our social sciences nga subject. So, one of the debaters ko and murag first time nako gyud nga kanang magdebate nga kanang mokuan sa imohang side unya naatlan pa gud to, ma’am, nga ang amoang dapat e-fight is ang side nga dili ko ganahan. Lisud kayo ng ingon ana nga fight bah and it was a challenge for me because it is my first time doing debates. Second is that I don’t like the side that I will be defending. I really have to research a lot about it especially when I want to win the debate. So in that experience, I really did my best, searched a lot of sources, and using the English language, I was able to defend it properly. And during that debate, I was given the award of the best debater.”

Trans: (“More engagements were given to me. Like, research or debates. It was my first time to be sent to join because in junior high school, I have never tried research at N.O.H.S. so there was no defense. In grade 11, I tried debate in our social sciences subject. So, I was one of the debaters and it was my first time being in a debate, like I had to air my side. Coincidentally, I belonged to the team that would fight for the side I wasn’t in favor of. It was really difficult and a challenge for me because it was my first time doing debates. Second is that I don’t like the side that I will be

defending. I really have to research a lot about it especially when I want to win the debate. So in that experience, I really did my best, searched a lot of sources, and using the English language, I was able to defend it properly. And during that debate, I was given the award of the best debater.”)

Participant 2 also had his share of experiences in terms of joining school activities. He recollected:

“When I was in elementary, my mother used to coach me in extemporaneous speaking, and I used to join in extemporaneous speaking contest within the division, and I think like the centerpiece of acquiring the language because I was able to master some of the techniques on how to speak, how to express. That’s why that experience is memorable to me even though it was like 8 or 7 years ago.”

Likewise, Participant 3 submitted himself to public speaking events in school which is what he enjoys the most. He shared:

“They saw my potential when I speak in English so they introduced me to different activities, to different contests using the English language and then, yeah, I was a broadcaster since elementary up till high school, a do speech also, then I am a host, I did some hosting gigs when I was in high school but not now because it’s pandemic.”

Theme 3: Numerous Learning Aids Utilized

The theme explores the strategies and initiatives that participants employed to enhance their knowledge of English and improve their English language proficiency. Some of the participants take advantage of books and literature to enrich their English vocabulary and comprehension. Others utilize the power of digital media and television, and then copy or imitate how English is spoken by those characters on TV. Some of the participants also make it a habit to speak English when talking with friends as well as interact with native English speakers.

Aside from reading books, Participant 3 turns to digital media to gain more learning:

“I’ve listened to many podcasts, Spotify podcasts, YouTube podcasts about English, because sometimes when you want to speak fluently in English, you need to listen to the native speakers so that you can apply the technicalities, those techniques, you need to listen to them and then I enjoy watching English movies rather than Filipino movies.”

Participant 4 does the same thing. She said:

“I usually watch videos online pag naa koy dili masabtan from my English teachers. Like for example kanang about sa grammar, wala kaayo siya gi

discuss ani nga college level.”

Trans: (“I usually watch videos online if there is something I don’t understand from my English teachers. For example, grammar was not fully discussed in this college level.”)

Participant 5, on the hand, considers her foreign boyfriend as a helpful instrument in her learning and familiarization of the English language as well as in boosting her confidence. She shared:

“Ako pong uyab, everyday na bya mi magstoryahanay for almost 5 years na, so everyday ko magstoryag English, so nakatabang siya kanang bahalag dili kaayo perfect, basta kay fluent2x naka gamay. Kanang mo face ka og tawo, confident na ka.”

Trans: (“My boyfriend as well...we talk every day for almost 5 years already, so I speak English every day. It helps me even though it isn’t totally perfect as long as I am a bit fluent now. I’ve become more confident when facing people.”)

DISCUSSION

Within the first theme, the participants articulated their gratitude for the support provided by their educators, which in turn bolstered their motivation to pursue their chosen fields. Ngo (2015) investigated Vietnamese students' motivation to learn English and discovered that their motivation increased when they felt connected with influential figures such as teachers, parents, and peers. Similarly, the research by Yusuf et al. (2020) revealed that teachers played a pivotal role in motivating students to learn English by imparting an understanding of the language's significance for their academic pursuits and future prospects.

The second theme elucidated that the participants engaged in school activities out of inherent enjoyment rather than external coercion, reflecting intrinsic/integrative motivation. Intrinsic motivation pertains to pursuing language learning for personal fulfillment, while extrinsic motivation entails utilitarian purposes. Ryan and Deci (2020) distinguished between the two, emphasizing that intrinsic motivation stems from personal desires for competence, pleasure, and intellectual stimulation, while extrinsic motivation is driven by external rewards or the avoidance of penalties.

Moreover, the final theme underscored the profound impact of activities such as reading books, viewing English language films and television shows, and regular usage of English in facilitating effective language acquisition. Pradana (2023) highlighted the constructive impact of judicious media and technology usage on learning, while Agustin et al. (2021) emphasized the positive influence of educational television content on academic performance. Furthermore, Hamad et al. (2019) study demonstrated that employing the YouTube videos and Audio Tracks Imitation (YATI) technique significantly

enhanced the speaking skills, fluency, and pronunciation of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners majoring in English.

In the context of reading, Lee (2021) underscored the role of extensive reading in developing superior command of the written language and diminishing writing difficulties. They accentuated that unrestricted reading serves as an exceptional source of knowledge.

Finally, engaging in conversations with native English speakers can substantially enhance English communicative ability. Zulfikar et al. (2019) found that students with positive attitudes toward learning English expressed a desire to communicate proficiently in English and interact with native English speakers. Suelto (2018) suggested that encouraging regular interaction with native English speakers can optimize students' English communicative ability.

Conclusions

The study emphasizes the transformative impact of a supportive educational environment on students' motivation and language acquisition. The unwavering encouragement from educators not only bolstered the participants' confidence but also fostered a deeper commitment to their academic and professional goals. This highlights the pivotal role of educators in shaping students' attitudes and perseverance in their learning journeys.

The findings also reveal the power of intrinsic motivation in driving sustained engagement and excellence in language learning. When students participate in activities out of genuine interest and personal satisfaction, they are more likely to achieve higher levels of proficiency and enjoyment in their studies. This intrinsic motivation propels students to actively seek opportunities for improvement and engage more deeply with the material.

Moreover, the study stresses the necessity of diverse and dynamic learning resources in enhancing language skills. The integration of books, digital media, and interactive activities provides a comprehensive approach to language learning, catering to different learning styles and preferences. The effective use of these resources not only improves language proficiency but also makes the learning process more engaging and enjoyable.

The significance of real-life practice, particularly through interactions with native English speakers, cannot be overstated. Such interactions offer invaluable opportunities for students to refine their communicative abilities and gain practical experience in using the language. This practical exposure is essential for achieving fluency and confidence in real-world settings. Overall, the study highlights that a holistic approach, combining supportive educational environments, intrinsic motivation, diverse learning resources, and practical language use, is crucial for effective language acquisition. These elements work synergistically to create a rich and stimulating learning experience, ultimately leading to greater academic and personal success for students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

1. Provide continuous professional development to strengthen teachers' capacity to motivate and support learners.
2. Implement mentorship programs connecting students with experienced and caring educators.
3. Design engaging, meaningful activities and recognize student achievements to build intrinsic motivation.
4. Offer learner-centered opportunities that align language learning with students' interests and passions.
5. Integrate diverse materials and multimedia resources to address varied learning styles.
6. Encourage the effective use of technology to enhance and personalize language learning.
7. Facilitate interactions with native English speakers through exchange programs or virtual platforms.
8. Promote real-world English use through debates, public speaking, campaigns, and similar activities.
9. Support language clubs or conversation groups to sustain regular practice.
10. Continuously evaluate and refine teaching approaches using student feedback and current research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the researchers ensured that all ethical protocols were rigorously upheld. Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained prior to each interview. The identities of the participants, along with any identifying details in their narratives, were kept strictly anonymous through the use of codes and secure data storage procedures. Confidentiality was protected at every stage of the research process, from transcription to analysis and reporting.

Given the reflective and deeply personal nature of phenomenological inquiry, the researchers created a safe, respectful, and empathetic environment during data collection. Participants were encouraged to describe their lived experiences at their own pace and were given ample time to express their thoughts and emotions without interruption. The researchers maintained a non-directive stance, intervening only to provide gentle prompts or clarifications when necessary, so as not to influence the participants' meanings or impose personal assumptions. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw at any point without penalty.

To uphold phenomenological sensitivity and bracketing, the researchers intentionally set aside personal biases and preconceptions, ensuring that participants' voices remained central and authentically represented. All collected data were used solely for academic purposes, and participants were assured that the findings would be presented in aggregate to avoid any possibility of individual identification.

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